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Formulation and Evaluation of Taste Masked Fast Dissolving Tablets of Risperidone by using Kyron T-104

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ABSTRACT

Risperidone, a benzisoxazole derivative, is an atypical antipsychotic drug with high affinity for 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) and dopamine D2 receptors. It is used primarily in the management of schizophrenia, inappropriate behaviour in severe dementia and manic episodes associated with bipolar I disorder. But this drug has bitter taste which may leads to patient's non compliance. Ion exchange resins are water-insoluble, cross-linked polymers containing salt forming groups in repeating positions on the polymer chain.¹ It can be used in the drug formulations to stabilize the sensitive components, sustain release of drug, disintegrate tablets and mask taste. Kyron T-104 is Ion exchange resin. Aim of this research work was to develop mouth dissolving tablet that disintegrates rapidly in mouth by using tasteless complex of Risperidone and Kyron T-104. Effect of different parameters such as swelling time, resin activation, drug resin ratio as well as stirring time was optimized by taste and percentage drug loading. Formulated DRC (Drug Resin Complex) was characterized by infrared spectroscopy. Tablets were formulated by direct compression with Kyron T-314 as super disintegrants. In these batches optimum hardness was achieved but disintegration time was found to be 20 second. Tablets formulated with 10% Kyron T-314 showed comparatively low disintegration time (20 sec), and friability (0.60 %) than the other batches. In present study we optimized the conditions required for maximum drug loading of Risperidone with Kyron T-104. Among different superdisintegrants was found suitable with drug-resin complex to get the low disintegration time and friability of tablets.

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Introduction

Among all route of administration, oral route is most important and preferable route of administration for solid dosage forms. Tablets are the most common solid dosage form, administered orally, but many patients specially children, mentally ill patients and geriatrics have problem in swallowing the tablets¹. Mouth dissolving tablets (MDT) have advantage of ease of administration and rapid onset of action. Further there is advantage of rapid disintegration without use of water in oral cavity². When MDT is kept in oral cavity then saliva quickly penetrates into tablet pores and causes rapid disintegration.

Risperidone, a benzisoxazole derivative, is an atypical antipsychotic drug with high affinity for 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) and dopamine D2 receptors. It is used primarily in the management of schizophrenia, inappropriate behaviour in severe dementia and manic episodes associated with bipolar I disorder. But this drug has bitter taste which may leads to patient's non compliance. Oral administration of bitter drugs with an acceptable degree of palatability is a key issue for health care provider, especially for pediatric patients. Conventional taste masking techniques such as use of sweeteners, amino acids, flavouring agent are often unsuccessful in masking the taste of highly bitter drugs. To mask the bitterness of drug various techniques are available, among those taste masking by use of ion exchange resin is most commonly used commercially². Ion exchange resins (IERS) are used to mask bitter taste of drug. Ion exchange resins are water-insoluble, cross-linked polymers containing salt forming groups in repeating positions on the polymer chain. It can be used in the drug formulations to stabilize the sensitive components, sustain release of drug, disintegrate tablets and mask taste.² The resin form insoluble adsorbates or resonates through weak ionic bonding with oppositely charged drugs so that dissociation of drug resin complex does not occur under the salivary pH conditions. Bitter cationic drugs can get adsorbed onto the weak cation exchange resin of carboxylic acid functionality to form the complex which is non bitter.

Aim of this research work was to develop mouth dissolving tablet that disintegrates rapidly in mouth by using tasteless complex of Risperidone and Kyron T-104. Effect of different parameters such as swelling time, resin activation, drug resin ratio as well as stirring time was optimized by taste and percentage drug loading were evaluated. Formulated DRC (Drug Resin Complex) was characterized by infrared spectroscopy. Taste evaluation of tablet was done.

Material and Method

Materials

Risperidone was obtained from Zim Laboratories, Nagpur, India. Kyron T-104 was obtained from Vama pharma, Nagpur, India. Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) from Gujarat Microwax Pvt. Ltd. India.

Methods

Formulation of drug resin complex

Formulation of DRC was done by the batch process; 100 mg of resin Kyron T-104 was placed in a beaker containing 100 ml of deionised water and allowed to swell for a definite period of time³. Accurately weighed amount of (drug: resin ratio) was added and stirred for desired period of time. The mixture was filtered and residue was washed with deionised water. Filtrate was analyzed by U.V. spectrophotometer at 279 nm for the unbound drug and percentage drug loading was calculated³.

Effect of concentration of resin on drug loading

An accurately weighed amount of Risperidone was added to the different concentration of Kyron-104 for the determination of optimized ratio with maximum drug loading⁴. Amount of maximum bound drug was determined at 279 nm by UV spectroscopy (Table no. 1).

Table no.1: Composition of all the formulation (B1-B3)

Sr.no	Tablet ingredient			
	(mg)	B1	B2	B3
1	DRC	4.7	4.7	4.7
2	Kyron T-314	5	7.5	10
3	Mannitol	60.84	58.34	55.84
4	Mcc	20	20	
20				
5	Aspartame	5	5	5
6	Talc	3	3	3
7	Mag.stearate	1	1	1
8	Aerosil	1	1	1
	Total	100	100	100

Table no. 2. Effect of drug resin ratio on DRC (Drug-Resin complex) formation using Kyron T-104

Resins	Ratio	% drug bound to resins
Kyron T-104	1:1	11.7
	1:1	25.2
	1:1	11.55
	1:1	14.25
	1:2	12.6
	1:2	15.75
	1:2	15
	1:2	11
	1:3	16.5
	1:3	0.3

Effect of pH on maximum drug loading

Accurately weighed Risperidone was added to 100 mg of Kyron T-104 solution and slurred in 100 ml each of pH 1.2, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 solutions (prepared from standard solutions of hydrochloric acid and potassium hydroxide), maintained at 25°C⁵. The maximum drug-loading at particular pH was estimated (Table no.2).

Effect of temperature on maximum drug loading

Accurately weighed Risperidone was added to 100 mg of Kyron T-104 solution and slurred in 100 ml of deionised water, maintained at different temperature such as, 40°C, Room temperature using temperature-controlled magnetic stirring for 6 hour⁶. Amount of maximum bound drug at the particular temperature was estimated (Table no. 4 and 5).

Table no.3. Effect of pH on DRC (Drug-Resin complex) formation using Kyron T-104

Resins resins	pH	Ratio	%drug bound to
Kyron T-104	5	1:1	11.7
	6	1:1	21
	7	1:1	11.55
	8	1:1	14.25
	5	1:2	12.6
	6	1:2	15.75
	7	1:2	15
	8	1:2	11
	8	1:3	16.5
	7	1:3	0.3

Effect of time on maximum drug loading

Accurately weighed, 100 mg of Risperidone was added to 500 mg of Kyron T-104 solution and slurred in deionised water. Three batches with stirring time of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 hr were processed⁷. Amount of maximum bound drug at the end was estimated (Table no. 6)

Characterization of Risperidone - Kyron T-104 complexes

The drug, resin and resinate were subjected to Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) studies to check drug resin interaction using FT/IR (Jasco – 470 plus).

Taste evaluation

Taste evaluation of DRC was performed by volunteers in the age group of 19 to 22 years. The study protocol was explained and written consent was obtained from volunteers. DRC equivalent to 10 mg Risperidone was held in the mouth for 30 seconds by each volunteer. Bitterness levels were recorded instantly and then after 30 sec, 60 sec. The bitterness level was recorded against pure drug using a numerical scale (Table no 9). A numerical scale was used with the following values: 0 = tasteless, 1= acceptable bitterness, 2= slight bitterness, 3= moderately bitterness and 4= strong bitterness⁸.

Determination of drug content

Resin ate prepared by above process was evaluated for the drug content. Resinate equivalent to 10 mg of drug was stirred with 100 ml of 0.1N HCl for 60 minutes, till the entire drug leached out, then the solution was filtered. Dilutions were made with 0.1N HCl and the drug content was noted spectrophotometrically at 279 nm using 0.1 N HCl as blank⁹.

Table no. 4: Effect of room temperature on DRC(Drug-Resin complex) formation Kyron T-104

Resins	Time (hr)	% drug bound to resins
KYRON T-104(room temp) pH-6 Ratio-1:1	0.5	20.60
	1	26.33
	1.50	33.21
	2	38.32
	2.50	44.12
	3	53.32
	3.50	58.45
	4	66.24
	4.50	77.21
	5	79.27
	5.50	85.44
	6	92.22

Table no. 5: Effect of temperature at 40°C on DRC (Drug-Resin complex) formation using Kyron T-104

Resins	Time(hr)	% drug bound to resins
Kyron T-104 At 40°C pH-6 Ratio- 1:1	0.5	18.21
	1	27.20
	1.50	36.45
	2	42.12
	2.50	50.22
	3	58.33
	3.50	66.77
	4	74.32
	4.50	82.24
	5	89.56
	5.50	94.35
	6	98.21

Table No. 6 Effect of time on DRC (Drug-Resin complex) formation using Kyron T-104

Resins	Time (Hr)	% drug bound to resins
Kyron T-104 pH-6 Ratio-1:1	1	82.11
	2	87.34
	3	91.21
	4	94.42
	5	96.23
	6	96.53

Table no.7 : Powder and tablet evaluation of optimized batch

Parameter	Optimized batch
Bulk density	0.535
Tapped density	0.614
Compressibility index	13.84
Hauners ratio	1.178
Angle of repose	28.52
Friability	0.60 %
Disintegration	20
Weight variation	100.1
Thickess	3.4
Diameter	5.3

Table no.8: Dissolution study of optimized tablet formulation

S.No	Time (min)	% Cumulative release
1.	5	83.51 ± 0.19
2.	10	98.12 ± 0.14

Table No. 9: Evaluation of taste resin ate

Volunteers	Bitterness level after					
	10 sec.	1 min.	2 min.	5 min.	10 min.	15min.
1	X	0	0	0	0	0
2	X	X	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	X	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0

***In Vitro* drug release study from resinate**

Resin ate equivalent to 4.16 mg of drug was subjected to dissolution studies using USP type II dissolution apparatus at 50 rpm with temperature of $37\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 900 ml of SSF (Simulated salivary fluid), similarly SGF (Simulated gastric fluid) was also used as the dissolution medium. Aliquot equal to 5 ml was withdrawn at specific time interval and it was filtered through what man filter, the solution was checked by UV spectroscopy at 279 nm and quantity of drug release was determined periodically¹⁰. The testing was carried out in triplicate.

Evaluation of the Tablet Blend

Physical properties such as bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, and the angle of repose of blend were determined¹¹.

Formulation and optimization

The tablet consist of resin ate equivalent to 30 mg drug. Avicel (PH 102) and Pearlitol SD200 were selected as diluents (Table No.1). All the 3 batches were prepared by direct compression method using single punch machine. The hardness of the tablet of each batch were tried to keep constant (3 kg/cm²). The weight of the tablet of each batch was adjusted to 100 mg. The tablet was evaluated for its tensile strength, weight variation, % friability, disintegration time (11, 12) (Table No.7).Dissolution study of tablets was carried out in simulated gastric fluids¹².

Results and Discussion**The bitterness threshold of Risperidone**

The bitterness threshold of Risperidone recognized by the volunteers was between 35-45 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. From the majority of volunteers it was found that the threshold value of Risperidone was found to be 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Optimization

While studying the effect of concentration of resin on drug loading, maximum drug loading was found in ratio 1:1 (drug: Kyron T-104). Complexation between the drug and resin is essentially a process of diffusion of

ions between the resin and surrounding drug solution. As the reaction is an equilibrium phenomenon, maximum efficiency is best achieved in batch process. Equilibrium time was shorter due to thinner barrier for diffusion of ions, as it is a continuous motion. Also higher swelling efficiency in the batch process result in more surface area for ion exchange. Hence the batch process is suitable for smaller particles. The swelling and hydrating properties of Kyron T-104 affect the rate of ion exchange, which in turn affects the percentage drug loading.

In unswollen resin matrix, the exchangeable groups are latent and coiled toward the backbone, hence less drug-loading efficiency. The optimized percentage drug loading (w/w) was found to be 98.10 ± 0.16 for Kyron T-104 with swelling time 30 minute. The equilibrium ion exchange in solution occurs stoichiometrically and hence is affected by stirring time. The optimized percentage drug loading (wt/wt) was found to be $98.12 \pm .14$ for Kyron T-104 with stirring time 60 minutes. Drug complexation involved exchange of ionisable drug and metal ion in resin. Such a mode of complexation between drug and resin affected by pH of media. Complexation was enhanced and was found maximum at pH 6. Efficient drug loading on Kyron T-104 in the experimental range $25-80^{\circ}\text{C}$. Increased temperature during complexation increases the ionization of drug and resin. The effect is more pronounced for poorly water soluble and unionized drugs. Higher temperature tends to increase the diffusion rate of ions by decreasing the thickness of exhaustive exchange zone. As Risperidone is water soluble ionizable drug, temperature does not show any significant effect on drug absorption and also cation exchange resins are significantly affected by temperature changes.

Taste evaluation by panel method

Taste evaluation revealed that Kyron T-104 masks the bitter taste of the drug completely.

Characterization

The interaction between the drug and the resin often leads to identifiable change in the IR profile of drug dispersion. So Risperidone: Kyron T-104 was subjected to IR analysis in order to evaluate possible interaction between drug and Kyron T-104 (Figure 1, 2). The drug content of resin was found to be $98.34 \pm 0.054\%$. Samples were withdrawn, analyzed at 279 nm and percentage cumulative drug release was determined. The presence of exchangeable ions of ionisable electrolytes in the salivary fluid may be responsible for this release. So the drug resin complex is stable in salivary pH for a period of administration. The amount released is insufficient to impart bitter taste while the formulation passes through the mouth to further parts of the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. *In vitro* drug release study was also performed in simulated gastric fluids (SGF) pH 1.2 (Figure 4). The drug release from Kyron T-104 was found to be more than 85 % within 10 minutes in simulated gastric fluids (SGF).

Figure no.1: FTIR spectrum of resin of Kyron T-104

Figure no.2 : FTIR Spectrum of Risperidone: Kyron T-104 Complex.

Dissolution study

Dissolution study of tablets revealed that more than 85 % of the drug was released within ten minutes (Table No 8).

Figure no. 3: Drug release from DRC (Drug-Resin complex) of Kyron T-104

Figure no. 4: Dissolution study of taste masked tablet

Conclusion

Use of cation exchange resin offers good method for preparing taste-masked substrate of Risperidone. Results obtained in this work show that drug-resin complex effectively masked bitter taste of Risperidone. Thus, complexation of Risperidone with Kyron T-104 increases acceptability and palatability of formulated rapid disintegrating tablets. The results of this study can also be extrapolated to other intensely bitter drug by suitable selection of resin.

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